

sheath already were developed at the time of submergence. In the second leaf sheath, the susceptible varieties showed earlier development of air space and had more of it than the tolerant varieties 10 days after seeding. The total number of air space in the first and second leaf sheath also was correlated negatively to

submergence tolerance ($r = -0.6657^*$).

The number of layers and thickness of the sclerenchyma layer of the first leaf sheath of the rice seedlings tested did not correlate with submergence tolerance. However, the tolerant varieties FR13A and Nam Sagui 19 showed one layer more than the other varieties. There are

variations in thickness in both tolerant and susceptible varieties.

Anatomically, the main significant difference between tolerant and susceptible varieties was in the percentage of the area occupied by air space and the number of air spaces. The more susceptible varieties had more air spaces. ■

Effect of flash flood on performance of some rice varieties

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An adaptive trial with eight popular, longduration entries was conducted at Block Seed Farm, Panskura, Midnapore District, West Bengal during 1978 kharif. These rainfed lowland entries represented tall indicas (NC1281 and OC1393), semidwarf cultivars (CR1014, CR1009, IET5656 and Pankaj) and a new semitall selection, CN540, along with Mahsuri.

Thirtyday-old seedlings of each cultivar were planted at 20- x 10-cm spacing in a 50-m² area during mid-July. The crop was deeply submerged by an unprecedented flood at 70 days after transplanting (end Sep) in 1978. The water depth was 3 m and the crop remained fully submerged for 10 days. Immediately after the flood water receded, it appeared that all the varieties had perished. But varieties with

Table 1. Effect of flash flood on the performance of some rice genotypes.

Variety	Hills counted (mean no.)	Hills surviving (mean no.) after flooding	Damaged hills (%)	Panicles (mean no./m ²)
CN540	49	43	12.24	152
Mahsuri	49	39	20.40	129
CR1014	49	33	32.65	85
IET5656	49	29	40.81	60
CR1009	49	9	81.63	9
OC1393	49	Nil	100.00	Nil
NC1281	49	Nil	100.00	Nil
Pankaj (check)	49	15	69.38	11

regenerative capacity subsequently developed fresh tillers from the live culms. After panicle emergence in the regenerated tillers, data on percentage of surviving culms and different yield attributes (number of tillers, panicle length, plant height, flag leaf length, number of fertile grains per panicle, exertion and total number of nodes per plant) were taken.

The two tall indicas, viz, NC1281 and OC1393, had no surviving culms, CN540 had 87.76% live hills after postflood regeneration and produced the most

panicles per square meter (Table 1). In terms of panicle yield per plant, panicle length, and number of filled grains per panicle, CN540 performed better than Mahsuri (Table 2). CR1009 produced a few panicles under similar conditions, but showed maximum sterility (88.65%).

CN540 represents a semitall plant type with long slender grains (9.7 x 2.3 mm). Its superior performance in rainfed lowland and flash-flood conditions might be an advantage over Mahsuri, a variety that has gained considerable popularity during kharif in India. ■

Table 2. Mean performance of 6 rice varieties with respect to different characters.

Variety	Panicle yield (g/plant)	Tillers (no./plant)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Flag leaf length (cm)	Fertile grains (no./panicle)	Sterile grains (no./panicle)	Exsertion (cm)	Nodes (no./plant)	Fertile-sterile grain ratio (F:S)
CN540	4.66	3.97	125.21	22.53	23.26	79.33	12.00	3.44	10.23	6.61
Mahsuri	3.08	3.14	119.07	16.35	18.03	62.93	9.21	4.20	10.06	6.83
CR1014	2.24	2.64	113.46	18.10	22.05	68.26	25.59	5.53	10.40	2.66
IET5656	1.60	2.15	83.73	15.67	15.86	35.88	13.22	—	11.23	2.71
CR1009	1.22	1.07	75.48	14.83	16.26	20.80	36.17	1.16	10.26	1.12
Pankaj (check)	0.85	0.86	76.81	15.69	19.44	42.11	22.05	0.73	9.33	1.90
LSD (0.05)	1.25	1.16	4.15	2.90	1.94	7.97	4.75	1.47	1.90	

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